

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT	 Gabii Project
GPR	2010	B		Min: 62.9391 Max: 63.1349	1276 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	

In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 1250 - 1251	Photo Model: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No #:
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DEFINITION Cut of a round pit below "Norco"	Covered by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Fills <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Filed by #SU: 1271
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HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction	FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition
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INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are			SOIL/MATRIX														
Anthropic	Geological	Organic	clay ___% silt ___% sand ___%														
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive <table border="1"> <tr> <th>Compaction</th> <th>Color</th> </tr> <tr> <td><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Hard</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Compact</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Friable</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Loose</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Soft</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)</td> </tr> </table>	Compaction	Color	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Hard	<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown	<input type="checkbox"/> Compact	<input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown	<input type="checkbox"/> Friable	<input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Loose	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red	<input type="checkbox"/> Soft	<input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow		<input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)
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UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)		Depth: <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original
Northern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Southern Limit	<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit → Norco's grave	
Western Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Eastern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE	
Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by:	Covers:
Is cut by:	Cuts: Floor level (1173)
Is filled by: 1271	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS
Cut of a pit, cutting the tufo floor of room 2 on its south-eastern corner as well as its wall (1186). Covered by "Norco's" grave (south-side)

DESCRIPTION
Position within sector: South of Area B, South-eastern side of Room 2.
Shape: ROUNDED -

For layers complete this section:
Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions):
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):
Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

For cuts complete this section:

Cut edges: rounded straight

Cut sides: straight concave convex sloping

Cut bottom: flat concave irregular

How is cut top edge? sharp rounded

How is cut bottom edge? sharp rounded

Observations:

For structural remains complete this section

Assignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) Irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material: Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
Size: Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cm

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

Foot/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

Cut of an Anthropie pit, cut into the tufo floor (= 1173) and in the wall (= 1186) -

cut covered by "Marco's" grave (= 1197)

Maybe related to the other Anthropie pit on the North (= 1191) -

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by MORGANE

on 27.07.2010

Revised by CLK

on 28.07.2010

PDFd by JJM

on 29.07.2010

Entered by

on